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Innovative silver-based capping system for mesoporous silica nanocarriers able to exploit a two-fold anticorrosive mechanism in composite polymer coatings: tailoring benzotriazole release and capturing chloride ions

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ABSTRACT: In this work, engineered stimuli-responsive mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) were developed and exploited in polymer coatings as multifunctional carriers of a typical corrosion inhibitor, benzotriazole (BTA). In detail, a new capping system based on a BTA/silver coordination complex, able to dissolve in acid and alkaline conditions and to simultaneously tailor the BTA release and the capture of chloride ions, was properly designed and realized. Acrylic coatings embedding the engineered MSN were deposited onto iron rebar samples and tested for their protective capability in acid and alkaline environments. Results highlighted the high potential of the proposed system for the protection of metals, due to the synergistic effect of the mesoporous structure and the capping system, which guaranteed both the sequestration of Cl⁻ ions and the on-demand release of the effective amount of anticorrosive agent able to ensure the enhanced protection of the substrate.

INTRODUCTION

Protection from corrosion mechanisms is one of the most relevant objectives for the improvement of the durability of civil and industrial structures made both of metals and metal reinforced concretes. Several strategies are employed to prevent or slow down the corrosion of these structures, starting from the optimized design and choice of protective materials and including periodic maintenance interventions. In this context, the application of polymer-based protective coatings, both onto metals and concrete surfaces, is a strategy widely exploited to prolong the service life of existing structures^{1,2,3}. However, when polymer coatings only act as passive barriers towards substances that could induce the degradation of the substrates, the protective effectiveness of the coatings is usually limited. For this reason, to promote their high-extent and long-lasting efficiency, polymer coatings are often doped with smart systems based on corrosion inhibitors, which protect metal and concrete structures by tailoring the release of anticorrosive additives under specific degradation conditions^{4,5,6,7} and by preventing the UV-induced deactivation of the anticorrosion agents⁶.

In order to modulate the release of the corrosion inhibitor^{8,9}, nanocomposite coatings embedding nanocarriers of active molecules represent a highly appealing approach^{10,11,12}. Promising nanocarrier candidates, able to carry high amounts of active molecules, are, for instance, micro or nanocapsules^{13,14}, inorganic nanotubes (i.e. halloysite)¹⁵ and inorganic nanoparticles^{16,17,18,19}. Among the latter, mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) are very attractive due to their easy preparation, high chemical stability and resistance, high porosity and surface area^{1,20,21,22}. Indeed, MSN have been already exploited as nanocarriers of corrosion inhibitors^{9,14,23,24,25} and, even more, as smart stimuli-responsive nanocarriers^{26,27,28,29}, able to release the active molecules in response to external triggers^{30,31,32}.

Various approaches are aimed at developing smart stopping systems, able both to promote the stimuli-responsive release of corrosion inhibitors under selected conditions and tailoring its releasing kinetics, thus ensuring efficiency against corrosion. A widely employed strategy is based on the formation of a coordination complex between 1,2,3-benzotriazole (BTA), a typical anticorrosion agent, and copper ions on the external side of high surface area nanocarriers. Lvov et al.^{15,33,34} first exploited this mechanism by loading halloysite nanotubes with BTA and inducing the formation of BTA-copper complexes at the edges of the inorganic nanotubes. In a recent work, Castaldo et al.⁹ exploited the same stopping system on MSN. The BTA-copper coordination complex was found to be an effective stopping/tailoring release system also for MSN, allowing the release of the anticorrosive agent over a wide acid exposure range.

Starting from this background, we aimed at developing an alternative BTA stopping/tailoring release system based on a different coordination complex. Our attention was focused on silver, another metal able to form chelating complexes with BTA^{35,36}, in which silver ions form a coordination net that may act as stopper tailoring the release of active compounds from porous structures.

An advantage of silver with respect to copper is the limited solubility of some silver salts, that allows to design a long-lasting stimuli-responsive release system. Moreover, the BTA-silver complex attains a two-fold function system: when the BTA-silver complex is slowly dissolved and the corrosion inhibitor is released, the free silver ions are available to exploit a capture mechanism towards specific anions, such as chloride ions, responsible for typical corrosion mechanisms in metal and concrete structures³⁷.

Moreover, despite their efficiency, the MSN-BTA system capped with copper ions showed an aesthetic drawback: the BTA-copper complex is characterized by a typical green-blue colour, that

limits its use for applications in which the protective coatings should not induce colour changes, such as cultural heritage applications³⁸. On the contrary, the BTA-Ag coordination complex is white, a more neutral colour for cultural heritage applications.

Thus, the effectiveness of the BTA-silver complex was tailored using MSN as nanocarriers, that are also able to protect BTA from the degradation caused by UV irradiation⁹. MSN loaded with BTA and capped with silver ions showed a pH dependent release of the anticorrosive agent, negligible at neutral pH and faster at low and high pH values, where the complex is slightly soluble. The capability of the co-released silver ions to capture chloride ions when the complex dissolves was also demonstrated. Finally, the innovative corrosion inhibitor nanocarrier system was validated in an acrylic polymer coating, applied for the protection of iron rebars. Loading the anticorrosive agent into the MSN allowed to embed in the coatings a certain amount of active agent which was slowly released when necessary, i.e. under an applied stimulus, therefore in a gradual way. This avoided the formation of BTA aggregates in the coating, which would eventually limit the anticorrosion efficacy of the active agents.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Materials

Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS), cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), triethanolamine (TEAH₃), 1,2,3-benzotriazole (BTA), silver (I) sulphate (Ag₂SO₄), hydrochloric acid (HCl, assay 36%), and ethanol were purchased by Sigma Aldrich (Milan, Italy). Bi-distilled water was also used for all the laboratory procedures. Iron-based disks were used as mock-up metal substrates (diameter \approx 1.2 cm, thickness \approx 0.7 cm). An acrylic resin dissolved in xylene (dry content 20-25 wt%) containing 1.5 wt% of benzotriazole (BTA) with respect to dry content, commercial name Metacril, was obtained from Antichità Belsito (Rome, Italy).

Preparation of the BTA-Ag complex

2.0 g of BTA were dissolved in 100 mL of distilled water and were treated with an excess of Ag₂SO₄ (about 4.0 g). The white BTA-Ag complex was collected through filtration, repeatedly washed with water and dried. About 3.76 g of BTA-Ag were obtained.

Synthesis of MSN

CTAB, TEAH₃ and bi-distilled water were stirred for 1 h at 80°C. Then, TEOS was quickly added in the mixture, which was stirred for further 2 h. After the hydrolysis and condensation of TEOS, MSN were formed and collected through filtration, washed with water and calcined at 600 °C for 6 h.

BTA loading into MSN

A solution containing 4.8 g of BTA dissolved in 60 mL of acetone at room temperature was adsorbed by MSN, previously dried under vacuum overnight. The loading procedure was divided in 6 loadings of 10 mL of solution, in order to increase the loading efficiency. MSN loaded with BTA were then treated with distilled water at 40°C for 1 h under stirring, in order to remove the

excess of BTA deposited onto the surface of the porous inorganic particles. These nanoparticles were centrifuged at 13.500 rpm for 10 min at 40 °C, then frozen using liquid nitrogen and freeze-dried overnight. These nanoparticles were called MSN-BTA.

Silver based capping layer onto MSN filled with BTA

1 g of MSN-BTA were immersed into 200 mL of a water solution of silver sulphate (20 mM), kept under mechanical stirring for 2 min, then centrifuged at 13.500 rpm for 10 min. The obtained nanoparticles, coded MSN-BTA-Ag, were collected through filtration, washed with water, separated by centrifugation, frozen in liquid nitrogen and freeze-dried.

Preparation of anticorrosion coatings

Iron disks as metal mock-up samples were lapped with SiC grinding paper, grit size P600, in order to obtain a smooth surface.

MSN-BTA-Ag were ultrasonicated and dispersed in a 1.5 wt% Metacril in xylene solution at 3 wt% with respect to the dry content of the solution. This mixture was deposited by drop-casting onto a series of iron disks to obtain coatings about 2 µm thick. The iron disks coated in this way were coded ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag and the applied coating contained an overall amount of 2 wt% of BTA with respect to the dry content of the acrylic resin (1.5 wt% in the commercial formulation + 0.5 wt% corresponding to the BTA from the MSN-BTA-Ag).

In order to compare the anticorrosive effect of the smart nanocarriers with respect to free BTA, iron disks were also coated with a Metacril solution containing additional BTA in the same amount as the BTA included in the MSN-BTA-Ag embedded in the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating (0.5 wt% of additional BTA with respect to the dry content of the product). These disks were coded ACR-BTA, and contained an overall amount of 2 wt% of BTA with respect to the dry content of acrylic resin (1.5 wt% in the commercial formulation + 0.5 wt% of free additional BTA).

Further iron disks were coated with Metacril containing the BTA-Ag complex and an overall amount of 2 wt% of BTA, coded ACR-BTA-Ag. In this case, the total amount of BTA consisted of 1.5 wt% free BTA from the commercial formulation and 0.5 wt% of BTA from the BTA-Ag complex.

Two additional disks were coated with an overall amount of free BTA of 3 wt% and 4 wt% with respect to the dry content of the acrylic resin, coded respectively ACR-BTA-3 and ACR-BTA-4, in order to verify the effect of BTA amount on anticorrosive efficiency of coatings. For comparison, iron disks were also coated with pristine Metacril and these disks were coded ACR. Before testing, all the iron disks were dried at room temperature for at least 48h, to ensure the complete solvent evaporation.

ACR-BTA, ACR-BTA-3, ACR-BTA-4 and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coatings were also prepared onto glass substrates in order to study how the coating morphology is affected by the BTA concentration and exclude possible defects due to the iron substrate roughness.

Characterization

Bright field transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis was performed on MSN, MSN-BTA and MSN-BTA-Ag. The nanoparticles were dispersed by mild sonication in ethanol with a Sonics Vibracell (Newtown, CT, USA) ultrasonic processor (500 W, 20 kHz) at 25% of amplitude for 5 min, then carbon coated copper grids were immersed into the dispersions and dried at room temperature. TEM analysis was performed using a FEI Tecnai G12 Spirit Twin (LaB₆ source) at 120 kV acceleration voltage (FEI, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and TEM images were collected with a FEI Eagle 4 k CCD camera.

Nitrogen adsorption analysis was performed on MSN and MSN-BTA-Ag using a Micromeritics ASAP 2020 analyzer (Norcross, GA, USA) and the Micromeritics MicroActive software for data

evaluation. N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms were registered at 77 K and specific surface area (SSA) was determined using the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) Total pore volume and pore size distribution were evaluated through the Nonlocal Density Functional Theory (NLDFT) using a model for oxide surfaces with cylindrical pores with a 0.1 regularization over the adsorption branch of the isotherm. The adsorption measurements were performed using high purity gases (> 99.999%); samples were degassed at 100 °C under vacuum before analysis ($P < 10^{-5}$ mbar).

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for MSN, MSN-BTA and MSN-BTA-Ag particles was performed by heating the samples from 25 °C to 800 °C with a rate of 20 °C/min in oxidative conditions, by using a Perkin Elmer Pyris Diamond TG/DTA (Waltham, MA, USA). Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was also performed on MSN-BTA-Ag to confirm the loading of the nanoparticles by means of a FEI Quanta 200 FEG scanning electron microscope (SEM, FEI, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) equipped with an Inca Energy System 250 and an Inca-X-act LN2-free analytical silicon drift detector (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon-on-Thames, UK).

The BTA-Ag complex obtained by precipitation of BTA with Ag⁺ was analysed by scanning electron microscopy **by** means of the above mentioned SEM in high vacuum mode. The precipitated was deposited in powder form onto an aluminium stub, sputter coated with a thin layer of Au/Pd and observed with a secondary electron detector. Moreover, the BTA-Ag complex was analysed by Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode, using a PerkinElmer Spectrum One (Waltham, MA, USA) FTIR spectrometer equipped with an ATR module, using a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ and 32 scan collections.

The kinetics of BTA release from the smart nanocarriers MSN-BTA-Ag was evaluated in water at pH 7.0, in HCl (pH 1.5, 4 and 5.5) and NaOH (pH 8.5, 10.0 and 12.5) aqueous solution. Tests were performed at 25 °C. MSN-BTA-Ag were dispersed in the tests solutions at the concentration of

0.015 mg/mL and the release of BTA was monitored by measuring at constant time intervals the BTA concentration of the solution through UV spectroscopy. BTA calibration curves in water, HCl and NaOH solutions were reliably collected. After the release tests performed with HCl at pH 1.5, SEM and EDX analyses were performed on the precipitated salt by means of the above mentioned SEM-EDX equipment. The precipitate was collected by filtration and dried under vacuum before analysis.

EDX analysis was performed on the iron disk in order to characterize their elemental composition. Then, iron disks coated with ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag, ACR-BTA, ACR-BTA-Ag, ACR-BTA-3, ACR-BTA-4 and ACR coatings were subjected to accelerated corrosion tests by (i) exposure to vapours of a 1.5 pH HCl solution at 60 °C for total 18 h and (ii) direct contact with a 12.5 pH NaOH solution for total 3 h at 40 °C. The evolution of corrosive phenomena onto the disks was monitored by a Lynx EVO stereomicroscope (Vision Engineering Ltd, Milan, Italy). In the case of direct contact with NaOH solution, before microscopy observation of the disks surface, the samples were washed with distilled water and dried with filter paper. The quantification of the corroded areas was evaluated through the ImageJ software with a consolidate procedure⁶. After the corrosion tests, SEM analysis was performed onto the corroded disks through the above mentioned equipment. Untreated ACR-BTA, ACR-BTA-3, ACR-BTA-4 were also analysed by SEM for comparison.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the novel BTA-Ag complex was prepared by dissolution of BTA in water and the subsequent addition of a silver ion water solution (see Experimental Section in Supplementary Information). The stoichiometric analysis of the collected precipitate indicated an approximate BTA/Ag ratio of

1:1. SEM analysis of the BTA-Ag complex (Figure S1) revealed that, in stark contrast to the morphology of pristine BTA, constituted by very large (millimetre sized) needle-shape crystals, the precipitated complex is constituted by platelets with irregular shape, with a lateral size ranging in a quite narrow range, approximately between 0.3 and 2.0 μm . FTIR analysis of the complex confirmed the occurrence of the chemical bond between BTA and silver ions. The FTIR spectrum of the BTA-Ag complex (Figure S2) showed the absorption bands typical of the C=C stretching (weak) in ortho-disubstituted aromatic rings, centred at 1580–1470 cm^{-1} , and the bands corresponding to out of plane C-H bending (strong) in the 780–700 cm^{-1} region. The absorption bands of the triazole ring (C=N and N=N, medium/weak) were found centred in the region 1450–1120 cm^{-1} . The strong absorption band centred at 1143 cm^{-1} was attributed to the formation of Ag(I)/N interactions in the BTA-Ag complex, as a consequence of the shift of the N-N-N stretching band originally centred at 1204 cm^{-1} in the pristine BTA^{39,40}.

Results of solubility tests of the BTA-Ag complex at different pH values revealed the pH-dependent solubility of the complex, low in all the investigated pH range (5-9), with a minimum at pH 7-8 and slightly higher at pH equal to or lower than 6 and equal to or higher than 9 (Figure S3).

Then, BTA was loaded in MSN nanocarriers and the novel BTA-Ag capping system was applied, realizing the MSN-BTA-Ag system. With this aim, MSN were synthesized through a facile high yield/high throughput procedure⁴¹. The MSN yield of reaction was about 98%. The mesoporosity of the obtained nanoparticles was evaluated through nitrogen adsorption analysis. The N₂ isotherm of the MSN is a type IV isotherm (Figure 1a), characteristic of materials with ordered porosity, with pronounced adsorption at very low relative pressure due to the presence of a fraction of smaller mesopores. Indeed, NLDFT pore size distribution (Figure 1b) shows a major pores size

distribution with the main peak at around 3.3 nm and a minor shoulder at 2.5 nm. MSN are characterized by a BET SSA of 700 ± 14 m²/g and a total porosity of 0.47 cm³/g. MSN-BTA-Ag were also analysed by nitrogen adsorption, showing a clear reduction of the accessible porosity and specific surface area with respect to the pristine MSN, which are reduced respectively to 0.31 cm³/g and 430 ± 9 m²/g.

The ordered porous structure of MSN is confirmed by TEM analysis, which reveals the MSN typical worm-like structure (Figure 1c-d). From images analysis the MSN diameter was evaluated as $90 \text{ nm} \pm 25 \text{ nm}$ (average value and standard deviation), all particles size ranging from about 50 to 140 nm. The formation of the BTA-Ag complex does not significantly alter the morphology of MSN. Indeed, only a thin dense layer can be observed on MSN-BTA-Ag external surface (Figure 1d), which can be attributed to the BTA-Ag complexes accumulated in the outer shell of the nanocarrier. As previously reported, studies on BTA-metal complexes have led to the identification of an energetic favourable “polymeric” BTA-Ag structure with silver connected to two N atoms (Figure 1e)^{42,43}.

Figure 1. Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms (a, adsorption in full symbols and desorption in hollow symbols) and NLDFT pore size distribution (b) of MSN (black squares) and MSN-BTA-Ag (red triangles); TEM images of MSN (c) and MSN-BTA-Ag (d) with schematic and chemical (e) representation of the BTA-Ag capping layer; TGA analysis of MSN (black squares) and MSN-BTA-Ag nanoparticles (red triangles) (f).

A quantitative evaluation of the amount of BTA loaded was obtained by TGA in oxidative conditions. MSN-BTA-Ag shows a significant degradation step at 400 °C, due to the thermo-oxidative degradation of BTA (Figure 1f). By comparison of the TGA traces of MSN and MSN-BTA-Ag, the amount of BTA loaded into MSN-BTA-Ag is estimated to be about 16 wt%. Considering the density of BTA (1.36 g/cm³), this amount corresponds to a filling with BTA of about 30% of the available MSN pore volume, in good agreement with nitrogen adsorption analysis results.

As hypothesized, the formation of the BTA-Ag complex does not alter the neutral coloration of MSN, differently from the typical blue colour of the BTA-Cu complex and the corresponding MSN-BTA-Cu system⁹ (Figure S4).

BTA release tests from MSN-BTA-Ag were performed in acid and basic conditions in order to characterize the kinetics of the BTA release from the nanocarriers at different pH values, which simulate different exposure conditions. Only 4 wt% of the loaded BTA is released in water at pH 7 (Figure 2a) also after prolonged release experiments. On the contrary, the BTA release is faster in all the acid conditions tested. Indeed, 92 wt% of BTA is released in 1 minute at pH 1.5, and in 20 minutes at pH 4.0. In both cases, complete release of BTA is achieved within about 2 hours. At pH 5.5 BTA release is slightly slower; about 86 wt% of BTA is released in 20 minutes and the complete release is achieved in about 4 hours (Figure 2a). In basic conditions (Figure 2b), a very fast release of BTA is observed at pH 10.0 and 12.5, with 95 wt% of BTA being released in 2 minutes at pH 12.5 and 90 wt% of BTA being released in 5 minutes at pH 10.0. In both cases, BTA is completely released within 150 minutes. On the other hand, the BTA release is low in moderately basic conditions (pH 8.5), where only about 6 wt% of BTA is released after 150 minutes (Figure 2b).

Figure 2. BTA release from MSN-BTA-Ag in neutral and acid conditions (a) and alkaline conditions (b).

This trend clearly indicates that the release mechanism of BTA is strictly correlated to the solubilisation of the BTA-Ag complex. At neutral or slightly basic pH, the nearly insoluble BTA-Ag exploits its capping ability, physically occluding the particle surface and preventing the release of the free BTA loaded in the internal volume of the MSN. On the contrary, at pH values far from neutral or slightly basic conditions, i.e. when the BTA-Ag complex mainly located on the surface of the MSN starts to be dissolved, the free BTA loaded in the internal volume of the MSN is progressively released.

The nanoparticles and the precipitate collected after the release tests performed in acid conditions by HCl (pH 1.5) were analysed by SEM and EDX analyses. Results showed the large presence of cubic shaped crystals among the MSN nanoparticles (Figure 3a,b). EDX analysis (Figure 3c) revealed the presence of Si, O, Ag and Cl in the sample, with Cl and Ag in the 0.96 ± 0.06 molar ratio, indicating that, upon release of BTA, the Ag^+ ions previously coordinated to BTA are able to react with the Cl^- ions, with consequent AgCl precipitation. This phenomenon is attributed to

the very low solubility of AgCl, which at 25°C exhibits a solubility product of $1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mol}^2/\text{L}^2$ ⁴⁴, this value meaning that only about 1.9 mg of AgCl is dissolved per liter of water.

Figure 3. SEM images (a, b) and EDX (c) results of the precipitate collected after the release test of BTA from MSN-BTA-Ag performed in acid conditions by HCl (pH 1.5).

Therefore, the BTA-Ag coordination complex employed as stopping system in the MSN-BTA-Ag smart nanocarriers forms a capping layer that acts as a pH-regulated net, tailoring the release of the active compounds depending on the pH of the environment. In particular, the release of BTA from MSN is inhibited in neutral conditions while it is modulated in response to acid or alkaline environmental stimuli. Moreover, linked to the BTA release is the capture of chloride ions, responsible for typical corrosion mechanisms in metal and metal-reinforced concrete structures³⁸.

In this way, the MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers are able to ensure both passive and active protection from corrosion in aggressive conditions involving Cl^- , by releasing BTA, which creates a protective layer adsorbed on the metal surface^{45,46,47}, and by releasing the silver ions, which neutralize the chloride ions through the formation of the AgCl precipitate. In Figure 4 the multiple anticorrosive mechanisms of MSN-BTA-Ag nanoparticles are schematized.

Figure 4. Representation of MSN-BTA-Ag anticorrosive mechanisms. In conditions far from neutrality, the BTA-Ag complex solubilizes and the BTA loaded in the internal volume of MSN is released from the silica mesopores, creating a passivating layer on the metal substrate. Moreover, in presence of chloride ions, Ag^+ reacts with Cl^- precipitating as AgCl .

The corrosion inhibition efficiency of the MSN-BTA-Ag particles was evaluated by accelerated corrosion tests for iron rebar samples coated with a polymeric 2 μm thin film containing the smart nanocarriers. The elemental composition of the iron disks was measured by EDX analysis, which revealed the presence of Fe (93.4 wt%), C (4.3 wt%), Mn (1.1 wt%), Si (0.7 wt%) and Cu (0.5 wt%). An optical image of the untreated iron disk is reported in Figure S5.

The polymer coating chosen is a commercial product largely used in cultural heritage application (Metacril), based on poly(ethylacrylate-co-methylmethacrylate) containing 1.5 wt% of free BTA with respect to the acrylic resin content. This approach was selected because it is generally accepted that, to maximize the effect of a smart nanocarrier containing an anticorrosion agent, the smart system must be added to a product that contains a certain amount of free anticorrosion agent^{27,48,49,50}. The free fraction of anticorrosion agent is able to improve the protection, whereas the nanocarrier acts as a reservoir of further anticorrosion agent, able to enhance and extend the protective effect of the coating and also protect the anticorrosion agents from UV degradation⁶. As detailed in the Experimental Section in Supplementary Information, the amount of MSN-BTA-Ag particles added to the commercial product was 3.0 wt% with respect to the acrylic resin content, corresponding to an additional 0.5 wt% of BTA. Applying this formulation onto iron mock-up samples, the coated ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag samples were obtained. Disks coated with similar amounts of the neat commercial coating (coded as ACR) and the commercial product containing additional 0.5 wt% of corrosion inhibitor dissolved (coded as ACR-BTA), thus with a total amount of BTA equal to that contained in ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag samples, were tested by comparison.

In order to test the efficiency of the smart nanocarriers in acid conditions, the coated mock-up samples were exposed to vapours of a pH 1.5 HCl solution at 60 °C. No appreciable differences among the disks covered with the commercial product (ACR), the product loaded with additional free BTA (ACR-BTA) and the product loaded with the smart MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarrier system (ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag) are recorded up to 5 hours (Figures 5a-c). Then, after 8 hours of exposure to acid vapours, the ACR disk starts to look noticeably more corroded than the others, with the appearance of 300-400 µm large dark areas (Figure 5d). At the same exposure time, the ACR-BTA rebar sample starts to show the first corrosion spots of 120-150 µm diameter, while the rebar coated with the smart ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating shows the presence of very limited corrosive phenomena (Figures 5e-f).

Figure 5. Optical images of iron rebar disks coated with: (a,d,g) commercial acrylic resin ACR; (b,e,h) commercial resin loaded with additional free BTA (ACR-BTA); (c,f,i) commercial resin loaded with the smart MSN-BTA-Ag system (ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag) after 5 (a-c), 8 (d-f) and 18 (g-i) hours of exposition to vapours of a pH 1.5 HCl solution at 60°C; SEM images of ACR (j), ACR-BTA (k) and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag (l, m) coated iron disks after 18 hours of exposition to vapours of a pH 1.5 HCl solution at 60 °C. EDX results (n) collected on bright nanoparticles evidenced in (m).

Indeed, the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag disk does not show significant signs of corrosion up to 18 hours, when the first corroded areas appear. At the same time, corrosion phenomena proceed on the ACR and ACR-BTA disks and the damaged areas are significantly larger (see Figure 5g-i). By image analysis, the area of the corroded zones in the optical images reported in Figures 5g-i was quantified, representing 4.1%, 3.1% and 0.7% of the total areas of the ACR, ACR-BTA and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag disks, respectively. SEM analysis confirms these results: the surfaces of the ACR and ACR-BTA samples are widely covered by corrosion products (identified as iron oxides by EDX), in large aggregates of 30-60 μm width in the ACR sample and in smaller aggregates of 10-30 μm width in the ACR-BTA sample (Figure 5j,k). At the same time, only isolated corrosion spots wide less than 5 μm are evidenced on the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag iron rebar samples (Figure 5l). Moreover, the effectiveness of the chlorine capturing by silver ions in the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag sample is clearly confirmed in the coatings by combined SEM and EDX analyses (Figure 5m,n). The presence of AgCl nanoparticles located close to the MSN, revealed as bright nanostructures with lateral size lower than 20 nm and whose composition is verified by EDX (Figure 5n), confirms the hypothesized chlorine capture mechanism. Once the BTA-Ag complex is dissolved and silver ions, released together with BTA molecules, get in contact with chloride ions, they precipitate in very small silver chloride nanoparticles. Therefore, results demonstrate the long-lasting efficiency of the protective coating containing the smart nanocarriers MSN-BTA-Ag, which inhibits the corrosion phenomena up to about 18 hours in the tested conditions, while the presence of free corrosion inhibitor in the same polymer coating inhibits corrosion up to only 8 hours. This enhanced protection is to be ascribed to both the sequestration of permeating chloride ions which are delayed and do not reach the metal substrate and to the modulated release of BTA

from the nanocarriers, which act as reservoir of the corrosion inhibitor, hosting and protecting it, and releasing it under stimuli. Indeed, the MSN-BTA-Ag particles embedded in the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating release the needed BTA to effectively contrast the corrosion phenomena. In this way, the triggered behaviour of the smart MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers constitutes an active response to the corrosion phenomena, thus ensuring longer protective efficiency in comparison to the polymer coating with the freely dispersed corrosion inhibitor.

The anticorrosive protection of the MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers was further tested in basic conditions. The ACR, ACR-BTA and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated disks were treated with a pH 12.5 NaOH solution at 40 °C and monitored by optical microscopy. In this case, the ACR and the ACR-BTA disks show the first effects of corrosion after 90 minutes, with the appearance of 100-200 µm corroded areas, while the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated disk are still quite undamaged at the same treatment time (Figure 6a-c). After 3 hours of exposure to NaOH, the first corrosion spots appear on the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated disk, while the corroded areas are significantly widened in the ACR and ACR-BTA coated disks (Figure 6d-f). In this case, corroded areas in the images reported in Figures 6d-f are quantified as the 8.0%, 2.5% and 0.1% of the total areas of the ACR, ACR-BTA and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated disks, respectively. SEM analysis performed on the samples after 3 hours of weathering in basic conditions confirms the large difference between the tested samples. Only small corrosion spots wide less than 5 µm are observed on the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated sample, while much larger corrosion areas are evidenced on the ACR and ACR-BTA coated disks (Figure 6g-i).

Also in this case, results demonstrate the major protective efficiency of the coating containing the smart nanocarriers. Indeed, although the alkaline testing conditions used are more aggressive than the acid ones, and the corrosion on all these samples starts at shorter time than in the acid tests, a

significant difference is shown among the samples coated with the acrylic resin, the acrylic resin containing free BTA and the samples coated with the resin containing the smart nanocarriers, which are able to release BTA on demand upon variable pH conditions.

Figure 6. Optical microscopy images of ACR (a,d), ACR-BTA (b,e) and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag (c,f) coated disks after 90 minutes (a-c) and 3 hours (d-f) of exposure to NaOH solution at pH 12.5 at 40 °C; SEM images of ACR (g), ACR-BTA (h) and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag (i) coated disks after 3 h of exposure.

The effect of the nanocarriers embedding BTA whose release is ruled by the silver capping layer was also compared to the effect of the BTA-Ag complex added to the commercial protective product in absence of the mesoporous silica nanoparticles (coated disk coded ACR-BTA-Ag). As shown in Figure S6, after the same treatments whose results are shown in Figures 5 and 6 for ACR,

ACR-BTA and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag samples, ACR-BTA-Ag rebars surfaces appear very damaged. The extent of the corroded areas after acid and basic treatments are similar or lower than the corroded areas shown by the pristine commercial product (ACR), but much higher than the corroded areas shown by either the ACR-BTA and the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag samples, confirming that the protective effect of MSN-BTA-Ag nanoparticles is to be ascribed to the combined effect of the smart nanocarriers acting as long-lasting reservoir with the tailored triggered release of anticorrosion agents and not only to the combined effect of the BTA and silver ions.

Moreover, accelerated acid and basic corrosion tests using the same conditions already reported for ACR, ACR-BTA and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated disks were performed on samples coated with the acrylic protective coating containing 3 and 4 wt% amounts of free BTA, namely ACR-BTA-3 and ACR-BTA-4. The quantitative results are summarized in Figure 7. Characterization on these samples revealed that, for ACR-BTA-3 coated disks, corroded areas covered 0.80% and 0.17% of the sample surface, after acid and basic exposition, respectively (Figures S7a,c). For ACR-BTA-4 coated disks, corroded areas increased to 1.14% in acid and 0.75% in alkaline conditions (Figures S7b,d). Therefore, the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating provides similar or higher protection to corrosion for the tested iron substrates in both acid and basic conditions than the acrylic coating containing free BTA, even when BTA is used at a concentration higher than 2 wt%. In particular, by increasing the amount of BTA to 3 wt%, the anticorrosion effectiveness of the coating to both acid and basic environments increases, and the extents of corroded areas in the tested conditions reach values close to those obtained with the ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating, but further increasing the amount of free BTA to 4 wt%, the coating efficiency slightly decreases again.

Figure 7. Corroded areas (%) of coated disks vs. total BTA concentration (free + loaded in MSN-BTA-Ag) for samples weathered in acid (a) and basic (b) conditions. The red dotted lines represent the extent of the corroded areas of the weathered ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coated samples.

Thus, the MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers show an anticorrosion effect better than that shown by protective coatings containing much higher amounts of free BTA. To have further indication about the mechanisms through which MSN-BTA-Ag nanoparticles are able to protect the substrate, SEM analyses on unaged coatings ACR-BTA, ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag, and ACR-BTA-3 and ACR-BTA-4 were performed to investigate the capability of BTA to form a continuous hydrophobic layer onto the metal substrate. Results, showed in Figure S8, reveal that BTA molecules tend to agglomerate at high concentration, as shown for the ACR-BTA-3 and ACR-BTA-4 coatings. These agglomerates prevent the formation of a continuous protective layer and represent defective points of the coating, whose presence explains the lower anticorrosion protection provided by

ACR-BTA-4. On the contrary, BTA agglomerates are not evidenced either in ACR-BTA either in ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coatings.

Moreover, the evidence that larger amount of free BTA are not useful to improve the protection efficiency of the substrate is supported also by theoretical considerations. The theoretical amount of BTA needed to totally cover the disk surface with a single BTA layer depends on the interaction of BTA molecules with iron-based surface. This interaction has been largely reported in literature, but the determination of the precise configuration of the complex is still uncertain⁵¹. In particular, depending on the metal, BTA is able to interact with the metals atoms on the surface through different configurations⁵². Reported BTA-Fe configurations suggest the BTA molecules density on iron surface can be higher than in other BTA-metal complexes, such as copper or aluminium^{49,53}. Basing on the hypothesized BTA-Fe structures^{41,49,54,55}, a BTA molecule could place slightly sloped by to the iron surface, due to the partial opening of the double bond between the nitrogen atoms, which allows their interaction with two consecutive Fe(II) ions on the substrate (see Figure S9). Considering the length of BTA molecule of about 0.6 nm and approximating its thickness to the atomic dimension, about 0.1 μg of BTA are needed to entirely cover a 1.2 cm diameter disk. This means that a 2 μm thick ACR-BTA coating, in which about 1 μg of BTA is embedded, already contains enough BTA to form a continuous protective multilayer adsorbed onto the iron surface⁴⁶.

Since these overall results and considerations, a possible schematic representation of the corrosion protection mechanism of ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag in comparison to a coating only containing free BTA is reported in Figure 8. The increase of BTA amount in the polymeric coatings does not ensure the formation of continuous barrier layers of anticorrosive agents on the metal surface, since most of BTA molecules aggregate, resulting unable to repair the anticorrosive layer when

corrosion starts. On the contrary, the higher protective efficiency of ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag coating is well explained by the slow smart release of BTA, which starts when the first aggressive species penetrate in the coatings and allow BTA diffusing through the coating and realizing an effective protective layer on the iron surface, minimizing the aggregation effect.

Figure 8. Schematic representation of the corrosion protection and failure mechanisms of the coatings ACR-BTA, ACR-BTA-x (i. e. ACR-BTA-3 or ACR-BTA-4) and ACR-MSN-BTA-Ag.

Thus, the MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers allow the tailored release of BTA, which can effectively prevent pits formation in metal structures. An excess of BTA in the coating matrix is not able to ensure a comparable protective effect, due to the BTA aggregation tendency at higher concentration. On the contrary, the tailored release of the anticorrosive agent from the MSN-BTA-

Ag nanocarriers prevents the formation of aggregates, guaranteeing a better formation of the protective layers with a higher and long-lasting anticorrosive efficiency.

CONCLUSION

In this work, new smart corrosion inhibitors nanocarriers based on high surface area functional mesoporous silica nanoparticles were developed. MSN were obtained through a high yield-high throughput synthesis and loaded with the corrosion inhibitor BTA through an optimized procedure. Then, a new pH dependent capping system based on a BTA-silver complex able to respond both to acid and alkaline triggers was designed and developed. In details, MSN-BTA-Ag nanocarriers were exploited to realize a multifunctional smart coating with a two-fold anticorrosive mechanism in aggressive conditions involving Cl⁻: a passive mechanism, based on the triggered release of BTA, which creates a protective layer adsorbed on the metal surface, and an active mechanism, ascribed to the silver capability to sequester chloride ions and thus to delay the permeation of aggressive species towards the metal surface.

All results demonstrated that:

- A) The BTA-Ag coordination complex is stable in neutral pH conditions and is able to tailor the BTA release in a wide pH range;
- B) Silver ions are effective in sequestering the chloride ions, thus contributing to increase the anticorrosive efficiency of the coatings;
- C) The exploitation of the concept of nanocarrier is an effective strategy to improve the anticorrosive protection of coatings, due to the on-demand release of BTA, which allows avoiding the formation of large BTA aggregates in the coatings and realizing a better covering of the metal substrates.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Additional experimental details, materials and methods and additional results

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Olivieri, F.; Castaldo, R.; Cocca, M.; Gentile, G.; Lavorgna, M. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles as carriers of active agents for smart anticorrosive organic coatings: a critical review. *Nanoscale* 2021, 13, 9091-9111.
- [2] Ulaeto, S. B.; Rajan, R.; Pancrecius, J. K.; Rajan, T. P. D.; Pai, B. C. Developments in smart anticorrosive coatings with multifunctional characteristics. *Prog. Org. Coat.* 2017, 111, 294-314.
- [3] Shchukin, D. G. Container-based multifunctional self-healing polymer coatings. *Polym. Chem.* 2013, 4, 18, 4871-4877.
- [4] Grundmeier, G.; Schmidt, W.; Stratmann, M. Corrosion protection by organic coatings: electrochemical mechanism and novel methods of investigation. *Electrochim. Acta* 2000, 45, 15-16, 2515-2533.
- [5] González-García, Y.; González, S.; Souto, R. M. Electrochemical and structural properties of a polyurethane coating on steel substrates for corrosion protection. *Corros. Sci.* 2007, 49, 9, 3514-3526.
- [6] Salzano de Luna, M.; Buonocore, G. G.; Giuliani, C.; Messina, E.; Di Carlo, G.; Lavorgna, M.; Ambrosio, L.; Ingo, G. M. Long-Lasting Efficacy of Coatings for Bronze Artwork Conservation: The Key Role of Layered Double Hydroxide Nanocarriers in Protecting Corrosion Inhibitors from Photodegradation. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 2018, 57, 25, 7380-7384.
- [7] Giuliani, C.; Pascucci, M.; Riccucci, C.; Messina, E.; Salzano de Luna, M.; Lavorgna, M.; Ingo, G. M.; Di Carlo, G. Chitosan-based coatings for corrosion protection of copper-based alloys: a promising more sustainable approach for cultural heritage applications. *Prog. Org. Coat.* 2018, 122, 138-146.

- [8] Rahsepar, M.; Mohebbi, F.; Hayatdavoudi, H. Synthesis and characterization of inhibitor-loaded silica nanospheres for active corrosion protection of carbon steel substrate. *J. Alloys Compd.* 2017, 709, 519-530.
- [9] Castaldo, R.; Salzano de Luna, M.; Siviello, C.; Gentile, G.; Lavorgna, M.; Amendola, E.; Cocca, M. On the acid-responsive release of benzotriazole from engineered mesoporous silica nanoparticles for corrosion protection of metal surfaces. *J. Cult. Herit.* 2020, 44, 317–324.
- [10] Shchukin, D. G.; Grigoriev, D. O.; Möhwald, H. Application of smart organic nanocontainers in feedback active coatings. *Soft Matter* 2010, 6, 4, 720-725.
- [11] Ghosh S. K. Functional coatings and microencapsulation: a general perspective. In *Functional coatings*, Wiley, 2006; pp. 1-28.
- [12] Shi, H.; Liu, F.; Yang, L.; Han, E. Characterization of protective performance of epoxy reinforced with nanometer-sized TiO₂ and SiO₂. *Prog. Org. Coat.* 2008, 62, 4, 359-368.
- [13] Latnikova, A.; Grigoriev, D. O.; Hartmann, J.; Möhwald, H.; Shchukin, D. G. Polyfunctional active coatings with damage-triggered water-repelling effect, *Soft Matter*, 2011, 7, 2, 369-372.
- [14] Huang, M.; Zhang, H.; Yang, J. Synthesis of organic silane microcapsules for self-healing corrosion resistant polymer coatings. *Corros. Sci.* 2012, 65, 561-566.
- [15] Abdullayev, E.; Price, R.; Shchukin, D.; Lvov, Y. Halloysite tubes as nanocontainers for anticorrosion coating with benzotriazole, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2009, 1, 7, 437-443.
- [16] Kartsonakis, I. A.; Balaskas, A. C.; Kordas, G. C. Influence of cerium molybdate containers on the corrosion performance of epoxy coated aluminium alloys 2024-T3. *Corros. Sci.* 2011, 53, 11, 3771-3779.

[17] Borisova, D.; Möhwald, H.; Shchukin, D. G. Mesoporous silica nanoparticles for active corrosion protection, *ACS Nano* 2011, 5, 3, 1939-1946.

[18] Mascia, L.; Prezzi, L.; Wilcox, G. D.; Lavorgna, M. Molybdate doping of networks in epoxy-silica hybrids: Domain structuring and corrosion inhibition, *Prog. Org. Coat.* 2006, 56, 1, 13-22.

[19] Mihelčič, M.; Gaberšček, M.; Di Carlo, G.; Giuliani, C.; Salzano de Luna, M.; Lavorgna, M.; Surca, A. K. Influence of silsesquioxane addition on polyurethane-based protective coatings for bronze surfaces, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 2019, 467-468, 912-925.

[20] Walcarius, A. Mesoporous materials and electrochemistry. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2013, 42, 9, 4098-4140.

[21] Guerritore, M.; Castaldo, R.; Silvestri, B.; Avolio, R.; Cocca, M.; Errico, M. E.; Avella, M.; Gentile, G.; Ambroggi, V. Hyper-Crosslinked Polymer Nanocomposites Containing Mesoporous Silica Nanoparticles with Enhanced Adsorption Towards Polar Dyes, *Polymers* 2020, 12, 6, 1388

[22] Rizzi, F.; Castaldo, R.; Latronico, T.; Lasala, P.; Gentile, G.; Lavorgna, M.; Striccoli, M.; Agostiniano, A.; Comparelli, R.; Depalo, N.; Curri, M. L.; Fanizza, E. High surface area mesoporous silica nanoparticles with tunable size in the sub-micrometer regime: insights on the size and porosity control mechanisms, *Molecules* 2021, 26, 42-47.

[23] Wang, M.; Chen, T.; Ding, C.; Fu, J. Mechanized silica nanoparticles based on reversible bistable [2] pseudorotaxanes as supramolecular nanovalves for multistage pH-controlled release, *Chem. Commun.* 2014, 50, 39, 5068-5071.

[24] Chen, T.; Fu, J. An intelligent anticorrosion coating based on pH-responsive supramolecular nanocontainers, *Nanotechnology* 2012, 23, 50, 505705.

[25] Ma, X.; Xu, L.; Wang, W.; Lin, Z.; Li, X. Synthesis and characterisation of composite nanoparticles of mesoporous silica loaded with inhibitor for corrosion protection of Cu-Zn alloy, *Corros. Sci.* 2017, 120, 139-147.

[26] Zea, C.; Barranco-García, R.; Alcántara, J.; Simancas, J.; Morcillo, M.; de la Fuente, D. pH-dependent release of environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor from mesoporous silica nanoreservoirs, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 2018, 255, 166-173.

[27] Fu, J.; Chen, T.; Wang, M.; Yang, N.; Li, S.; Wang, Y.; Liu, X. Acid and alkaline dual stimuli-responsive mechanized hollow mesoporous silica nanoparticles as smart nanocontainers for intelligent anticorrosion coatings, *ACS Nano* 2013, 7, 12, 11397-11408.

[28] Yeganeh, M.; Asadi, N.; Omid, M.; Mahdavian, M. An investigation on the corrosion behavior of the epoxy coating embedded with mesoporous silica nanocontainer loaded by sulfamethazine inhibitor, *Prog. Org. Coat.* 2019, 128, 75-81.

[29] Maia, F.; Tedim, J.; Lisenkov, A. D.; Salak, A. N.; Zheludkevich, M. L.; Ferreira, M. G. Silica nanocontainers for active corrosion protection, *Nanoscale* 2012, 4, 4, 1287-1298.

[30] Ding, C.; Liu, Y.; Wang, M.; Wang, T.; Fu, J. Self-healing, superhydrophobic coating based on mechanized silica nanoparticles for reliable protection of magnesium alloys, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2016, 4, 21, 8041-8052.

[31] Maggini, L.; Cabrera, I.; Ruiz-Carretero, A.; Prasetyanto, E. A.; Robinet, E.; De Cola, L. Breakable mesoporous silica nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery. *Nanoscale* 2016, 8, 13, 7240-7247.

[32] Chen, T.; Fu, J. pH-responsive nanovalves based on hollow mesoporous silica spheres for controlled release of corrosion inhibitor, *Nanotechnology* 2012, 23, 23, 235605.

- [33] Abdullayev, E.; Lvov, Y. Clay nanotubes for corrosion inhibitor encapsulation: release control with end stoppers, *J. Mater. Chem.* 2010, 20, 32, 6681-6687.
- [34] Fix, D.; Andreeva, D. V.; Lvov, Y. M.; Shchukin D. G.; Möhwald, H. Application of inhibitor-loaded halloysite nanotubes in active anti-corrosive coatings, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* 2009, 19, 11, 1720-1727.
- [35] Richardson, C.; Steel, P. J. Benzotriazole as a structural component in chelating and bridging heterocyclic ligands; ruthenium, palladium, copper and silver complexes, *Dalton Trans.* 2003, 5, 992-1000.
- [36] Cheng, K. L. Determination of Silver with 1, 2, 3-Benzotriazole. *Anal. Chem.* 1954, 26, 6, 1038-1040.
- [37] Ma, Q.; Nanukuttan, S. V.; Basheer, P. M.; Bai, Y.; Yang, C. Chloride transport and the resulting corrosion of steel bars in alkali activated slag concretes. *Mater. Struct.* 2016, 49, 9, 3663-3677.
- [38] Artesani, A.; Di Turo, F.; Zucchelli, M.; Traviglia, A. Recent advances in protective coatings for cultural heritage – an overview. *Coatings* 2020, 10, 3, 217.
- [39] Rubim, J.; Gutz, I. G. R.; Sala, O.; Orville-Thomas, W. J.; Surface enhanced Raman spectra of benzotriazole adsorbed on a copper electrode, *J. Mol. Struct.* 1983, 100, 571-583.
- [40] Salorinne, K.; Chen, X.; Troff, R.W.; Nissinena, M.; Häkkinen, H. One-pot synthesis and characterization of subnanometre-size benzotriazolate protected copper clusters, *Nanoscale* 2012, 4, 4095.
- [41] Zhang, K.; Xu, L. L.; Jiang, J. G.; Calin, N.; Lam, K. F.; Zhang, S. J.; Wu, H. H.; Wu, G. D.; Albela, B.; Bonnevoit, L.; Wu, P. Facile Large-Scale Synthesis of Monodisperse Mesoporous Silica Nanospheres with Tunable Pore Structure, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 2013, 135, 7, 2427-2430.

[42] Naumov, S.; Kapoor, S.; Thomas, S.; Venkateswaran, S.; Mukherjee, T. SERS of benzotriazole on Ag colloid: Surface structure characterization using the DFT approach. *J. Mol. Struct.: THEOCHEM* 2004, 685, 1-3, 127-131.

[43] Cao, P. G.; Yao, J. L.; Zheng, J. W.; Gu, R. A.; Tian, Z. Q. Comparative study of inhibition effects of benzotriazole for metals in neutral solutions as observed with surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy. *Langmuir* 2002, 18, 1, 100-104.

[44] Wang, J.; An, C.; Zhang, M.; Qin, C.; Ming, X.; Zhang, Q. Photochemical conversion of AgCl nanocubes to hybrid AgCl–Ag nanoparticles with high activity and long-term stability towards photocatalytic degradation of organic dyes. *Canadian Journal of Chemistry* 2012, 90, 10, 858-864.

[45] Biswas, R. K.; Khan, P.; Mukherjee, S.; Mukhopadhyay, A. K.; Ghosh, J.; Muraleedharan, K. Study of short range structure of amorphous Silica from PDF using Ag radiation in laboratory XRD system, RAMAN and NEXAFS. *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids* 2018, 488, 1-9.

[46] Ha, H.; Payer, J. The effect of silver chloride formation on the kinetics of silver dissolution in chloride solution, *Electrochim. Acta* 2011, 56, 7, 2781-2791.

[47] Mansfield, F.; Smith, T.; Parry, E. P. Benzotriazole as corrosion inhibitor for copper, *Corrosion* 1971, 27, 7, 289-294.

[48] Kuznetsov, Y. I.; Andreeva, N. P.; Agafonkina, M. O. On intensification of iron passivation by benzotriazole in aqueous solutions. *Prot. Met. Phys. Chem. Surf.* 2010, 46, 5, 603-608.

[49] Tromans, D.; Li, G. Growth of passivating CuBTA films on copper in aqueous chloride/benzotriazole solutions, *Electrochem. Solid-State Lett.* 2001, 5, 2, B5.

[50] Chen, T.; Chen, R.; Jin, Z.; Liu, J. Engineering hollow mesoporous silica nanocontainers with molecular switches for continuous self-healing anticorrosion coating, *J. Mater. Chem. A*, 2015, 3, 18, 9510–9516.

[51] Xie, Z. H.; Li, D.; Skeete, Z.; Sharma, A.; Zhong, C. J. Nanocontainer-enhanced self-healing for corrosion-resistant Ni coating on Mg alloy, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 2017, 9, 41, 36247–36260.

[52] Wang, T.; Tan, L.; Ding, C.; Wang, M.; Xu, J.; Fu, J. Redox-triggered controlled release systems-based bi-layered nanocomposite coating with synergistic self-healing property, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2017, 5, 4, 1756–1768.

[53] Kokalj, A. Ab initio modeling of the bonding of benzotriazole corrosion inhibitor to reduced and oxidized copper surfaces, *Faraday discuss.* 2015, 180, 415-438.

[54] Kovačević, N.; Kokalj, A. Chemistry of the interaction between azole type corrosion inhibitor molecules and metal surfaces. *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 2012, 137, 1, 331-339.

[55] Finšgar, M.; Milošev, I. Inhibition of copper corrosion by 1, 2, 3-benzotriazole: a review. *Corros. Sci.* 2010, 52, 9, 2737-2749.

[56] Petrunin, M.; Maksaeva, L.; Gladkikh, N.; Makarychev, Y.; Maleeva, M.; Yurasova, T.; Nazarov, A. Thin benzotriazole films for inhibition of carbon steel corrosion in neutral electrolytes. *Coatings* 2020, 10, 4, 362.

[57] Cao, P. G.; Gu, R. A.; Tian, Z. Q. Electrochemical and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy studies on inhibition of iron corrosion by benzotriazole. *Langmuir* 2002, 18, 20, 7609-7615.